

MICROWAVE NONDESTRUCTIVE INVESTIGATION OF MULTIPLE IMPACTED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring lifetime degradation of composites is a critical issue in applications having extended life expectancies, such as infrastructure and industrial equipment. In this study, damage onset, the changing damage signature and damage accumulation are investigated. An impact fatigue test machine introduces low energy, multiple impact damage and changes in the impact curve load ramps are related to evolving damage. To further understand the damage signature, microwave nondestructive investigation is used to examine microstructural aspects of damage initiation and growth. Damage patterns specific to woven composites are discovered prior to visible damage and are also related to visible high cycle delamination.

INTRODUCTION

As fiber reinforced composite materials mature and become more commonplace they are being considered for an ever increasing number, and variety, of applications. The carefully monitored operating environments of the high technology industries which have constituted the bulk of composite structural applications are becoming less common as composite materials technology moves into the arenas of infrastructure, automotive and industrial equipment. In many of these new applications extended lifetimes are expected under conditions of repetitive loading and multiple impact. The damage which results can grow slowly, as do fatigue flaws, and ultimately can cause catastrophic failure. Existing predictive capabilities do exist for cyclic loading such as fatigue, as well as for the degradation of the material after sustaining a single impact; however, the mechanisms of repetitive high cycle impact damage are not well understood.

Lifetime predictions have been a problem particularly due to the difficulties encountered in identifying early stages of damage and monitoring lifetime damage accumulation in composites. It has been hypothesized that there is a build-up of micro damage, such as matrix micro-cracks and micro-delaminations, even though there is no apparent change in material compliance. A critical level is finally reached at which time the properties of the composite begin to fall and compliance change is evident. Often, by the time significant compliance change is measured, damage has progressed to a stage that repair is difficult if not impractical.

Previous researchers have investigated the impact fatigue phenomena through repetitive drop-weight testing, with typical durations of up to 1000 cycles [1,2,3,4]. For studying the effects of extremely low energy multiple impact, it has been necessary to develop specialized test equipment capable of operating continuously at high cyclic rates. The test apparatus used in this work was originally designed to enable one million cycles of impact to be introduced into composite tube/metal end fitting bonded joints in a 24 hour period [5]. This was necessary to gain information critical to the design of a composite replacement body-maker ram in a high speed aluminum can forming operation. However, this same test apparatus has proven extremely useful as a tool to introduce cumulative, low energy damage into composite laminates for impact damage initiation and propagation studies.

In addition to the limitations of testing capabilities, and of current understanding of mechanisms leading to damage initiation and propagation in composite materials, present techniques of early detection are few and are often difficult to apply in a service environment. Ultrasonic techniques are commonly applied to composites and are based on the amplitude attenuation of a longitudinal wave pulse. Attenuation can either be measured by through-transmission techniques or by pulse-echo. The pulse-echo technique, which requires access to only one side of the structure, is most commonly used for in-situ inspection. Unfortunately, the pulse-echo principle requires precise entry angle alignment and suffers from increased signal processing complexity. Both ultrasonic approaches require a couplant, typically water, which can also interact with the composite and can potentially be a source of material degradation [6,7]. X-ray techniques have also been used to evaluate composite materials for damage. Such techniques have been shown to offer accurate determination of void size down to the nanometer scale, but the resulting images are only 2-D representations and depth information is lost. This limitation can be overcome, at great expense, through the use of computer tomography X-ray imaging where 3-D images are generated. However, the processing of the X-ray film becomes expensive and does not allow for real time imaging [6,8,9]. Other techniques that have been applied to the investigation of damage in composites include infrared thermography and eddy current testing [10].

Microwave nondestructive investigation (NDI) techniques possess certain advantages over the other NDI approaches mentioned. In particular, microwave NDI is well suited to inspecting dielectric materials such as polymers, ceramics, and glass fiber reinforced composites. This is partially due to the fact that microwaves easily penetrate dielectric materials and the reflected or transmitted signal can be related to dielectric properties of the material. Subsequently, physical and mechanical properties can be determined based on these microwave signals. It is this ability to yield information relating to the changing physical properties of materials that makes the application of microwave NDI, to damage detection in composites, so interesting [11]. It has recently been shown that small variations in the degree of porosity in composite materials can be ascertained through the use of microwave reflection techniques [12]. Further, it has been shown that low levels of impact damage in composite laminates can be sensed by this technique [13].

In an extension of these works, involving impact fatigue testing and microwave NDI, this paper investigates the potential to combine damage information from these two approaches with higher order vibration mode information acquired during impact fatigue loading. Previous efforts by other researchers have used vibration information from composite structural components to monitor delamination damage in-situ [14]. However, this present effort involves laboratory controlled testing and attempts to determine damage information at levels more commonly considered to be in the initiation regime rather than in later stages of damage. Thus, the ultimate goal is to develop an understanding of the damage signature inherent to various levels and forms of cumulative damage in composite materials.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The general experimental approach applied to these composite test specimens was to introduce cumulative damage by multiple, low energy impact. At predetermined intervals, the specimens were evaluated visually, and by microwave scanning, for signs of damage. Microwave damage maps were plotted at each interval and impact load curves recorded. The microwave NDI results were compared to visible details and to changes in mechanical performance recorded by the impact fatigue apparatus.

MULTIPLE IMPACT TEST SPECIMENS

Multiple impact test specimens were molded in a disk geometry of 63.5 mm diameter and 3.0 mm thickness. These composite specimens were made up of 8 layers of 10 oz. satin weave fiberglass fabric in an epoxy matrix. The plies were stacked in a mid-plane symmetric, quasi-isotropic fashion with a fiber volume fraction of approximately 35%. Cure was performed at room temperature and care was taken during mold filling to minimize the inclusion of air. Finally, specimens were carefully ground and polished, to a final thickness of 2.15 ± 0.05 mm, to ensure flat and parallel surfaces for optimal microwave NDI sensitivity and minimal baseline correction.

MULTIPLE IMPACT TEST TECHNIQUE

Multiple impact testing involves impacting a single specimen a large number of times while measuring the resulting changes in the load versus time history [15]. The lack of a standardized test capable of rapid, high cycle impact fatigue made it necessary to develop custom test equipment. The test machine developed uses an electrically driven ram that impacts a stationary disk shaped specimen which is rigidly clamped. The diameter of the unsupported portion of the disk is 38.1 mm. A dynamic load cell capable of measuring an impact load of up to 22.25 kN is attached to the moving ram and a 12.7 mm diameter ball indenter is attached to the load cell as shown in Fig.1. The resulting out-of-plane impact information is recorded using computer data acquisition at a sampling rate of 45 kHz and, for certain tests, a high speed oscilloscope at a rate of 250 kHz. The number of impacts, peak impact load, and the shape of the impact pulse are recorded for further analysis. The test apparatus was designed to generate impact pulses comparable to impact events resulting from drop-weight test procedures, but at a rate of 11 impacts per second. The load cell measures the load throughout each impact pulse and the energy absorbed by the specimen is then derived from the recorded curve. Individual impact energies are adjustable from approximately 0.02 - 1.5 joules.

For these tests the plate center deflection was set to 0.25 mm, resulting in a dynamic load of 0.24 kN. The corresponding energy of impact is approximately 0.03 J. This very low value of impact energy is significantly below stated single impact damage energies for fiber reinforced composites, thus requiring hundreds of cycles before initiation of visible damage [16]. The specimens were impacted for 330 cycles at a time. After each set of cycles the specimen was removed from the impact fatigue machine and transferred to the X-Y scanning microwave test apparatus. Microwave measurements were recorded and the specimen was once again mounted in the impact fatigue tester, and the test cycle repeated. These cycles of multiple impact damage and microwave measurement were continued until significant visible damage was observed.

MICROWAVE NDI TEST TECHNIQUE

A single-sided reflection type measurement system, operating at 34.8 GHz, and using an open-ended rectangular waveguide sensor was utilized to produce the microwave images. Fig.2 shows the side and plan views of an open-ended rectangular waveguide sensor scanning a glass

Figure 1. Impact Fatigue Setup.

Figure 2. Scanning Microwave Setup.

fiber reinforced epoxy composite sample. As the open-ended rectangular waveguide transmits a signal into the composite a voltage related to the magnitude of the reflection coefficient, at the waveguide aperture, is continuously recorded while the waveguide scans over the composite. The X-Y scan is controlled by a computer stepper system and the data is automatically recorded in a 1.0 mm x 1.0 mm grid over a 18 mm x 20 mm area centered at the point of impact. The microwave apparatus is similar in concept to a single coupler reflectometer [17].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MULTIPLE IMPACT TEST RESULTS

The use of impact fatigue testing allows the introduction of low energy, cumulative damage which enables control of damage initiation and propagation rates. Initially this test machine was developed for investigating the shear performance of adhesive bonded joints between composite tubes and steel inserts. In these tests, the degradation of the adhesive joint led to a substantial drop in the joint stiffness and thus, a major increase in compliance was measured during the specimen lifetime. Results for such tests can be shown as lifetime history diagrams which are plots of load versus number of impacts [5,15]. After some number of cycles, the accumulated damage in the bondline reaches a critical level and the impact load begins to drop as the joints become increasingly compliant.

For the specimens in this work, the area of damage is a small fraction of the total plate area. As a result, a measurable compliance change is not seen during testing of this configuration. However, on examination of the impact load curves, a broadening of the loading ramp is recorded as the number of cycles of impact increases (Fig.3). This indicates changes in higher order modes of vibration of the system brought on by small scale variations in specimen compliance or damping. The investigation of the relation of this changing load ramp to damage is presently in a preliminary state. To determine if significant information exists in this region of broadening in the load ramp, higher speed data acquisition was used. A pair of impact pulse load ramps acquired at 250 kHz are shown in Fig. 4. This figure shows two 0.32 kN impact pulses separated by approximately 300 cycles. No appreciable change in visible damage occurred during this period; however, some minor delamination damage was apparent prior to the first impact pulse. The changing nature of the vibration measured on the load ramp seems to correspond to increasing damage in the specimen and may form a basis for monitoring various stages of damage.

For these test specimens visible damage begins as a small indentation at the point of impact contact. With continued cycles of impact some fine cracks begin to appear, emanating from the point of impact into the specimen. Further impacts lead to the introduction of minor delamination

Figure 3. Impact Load-Time Curves (45 kHz sampling rate).

Figure 4. Impact Load-Time Curves (250kHz sampling rate).

in the composite at the bundle crossover points of the weave. Visible delamination is noted by an increase in opacity, as seen in Fig.5. Finally, the local disbonded regions coalesce, and the delamination grows radially outward from the point of impact. Significant broadening in the load ramp of the impact pulse seems to correspond with the onset of delamination; however, more subtle load ramp variations have also been noted during earlier cycles of impact.

MICROWAVE NDI TEST RESULTS

Once the microwave frequency and waveguide standoff distance were optimized the system gave excellent images of the damage region. Fig.6 shows a typical microwave surface map of the central region of a composite disk after 4000 impacts at a nominal load of 0.32 kN. This level of damage is similar to that of the specimen corresponding to the impact pulses of Fig.3 and to the visible damage apparent in Fig.5. The primary impact region can be readily observed near the center of the map. It is seen that this region is not circular as might be expected in an isotropic specimen, but actually shows accelerated damage along the fiber bundles. The regularly repeating vertical features on the surface map correspond to the fiber bundles in the composite. Thus, this central zone of the microwave damage map shows, by changing intensity of reflected signal related to changing density, the presence of delamination damage.

To study the early stages of initiation and development of damage, microwave maps were acquired at fixed increments. Fig.7 shows three sequential maps of the same specimen after 0, 330 and 990 cycles of impact at a 0.24 kN load. The initial unimpacted case serves as a baseline

Figure 5. Fiberglass Impact Specimen.

Figure 6. Microwave Map - 4000 cycles/0.32 kN.

Figure 7. Microwave Maps of Sequential Multiple Impact Damage (0.24 kN).

map. Changes are evident in the maps of 330 cycles and beyond, with the microwave signature becoming more evident and more extensive as the impact cycles progress. Even after 990 cycles, no delamination is visible and no noticeable change has occurred since the 330 cycle test, when some minor matrix cracking was seen. This minor matrix cracking, or crazing, was not apparent in microwave maps, indicating an area where future experimental efforts must concentrate.

The changing microwave signal that is evident with increasing cycles of impact corresponds to locations of warp/weave crossover in the fiberglass composite. These areas are locations of high stress concentration under bending conditions. The sequence of microwave damage maps clearly indicates the presence of damage induced debond initiation, or at least some form of porosity, at these positions in the weave. Further, the microwave maps may be an indication of local molecular level changes in the matrix material or in the fiber/matrix interface. With continued impact loading, more points of damage initiation become apparent at new warp/weave crossover locations and finally begin to coalesce as previously suggested. The microwave maps suggest damage progressing along fiber bundles from the warp/weave crossovers. As a check of the registration between the microwave maps and the specimen structure, interbundle distances were compared. The results were in very close agreement, with bundle widths of roughly 1.5 mm. Thus, the microwave technique seems to yield significant indications of damage, even at stages of growth preceding visible delamination.

As an independent test of the mapped damage evolution, a 4-ply disk was impacted at a higher load of 0.53 kN for 500 cycles. No visible delamination damage or interply cracking was noticeable; however, as seen in Fig. 8, the scanning microwave technique clearly results in a signal at the warp/weave crossovers of the fiberglass fabric. This microwave map closely matches the results described for the 8-ply test sequence and indicates a similar mode of damage development, suggesting that this may be common trend for woven fabric composites.

Figure 8. Microwave Map at Point of Impact.

SIGNIFICANCE OF RESULTS

As described in the previous sections, the results of this investigation show that microwave NDI techniques can yield information related to the developing damage in fiber reinforced composites. The maps of the changing microwave intensity indicate that damage in these woven fiber composites is initiating at warp/weave intersections near the point of impact and growing outward along fiber directions. The increasing severity of damage and the expanding damage zone is seen in the microwave maps. Further, the impact results compare closely to visible damage at higher numbers of cycles and to the changes apparent in the impact pulse load-time history.

It is interesting to realize from this data that the microwave maps indicate the initiation of damage prior to visual recognition. In addition, in each test set the region of damage indicated by the microwave technique seems slightly larger than that visually observed. The averaging of damaged and undamaged regions at the boundary of the waveguide does not fully account for this phenomenon, and it seems apparent that some level of damage is being discerned by microwave NDI which is not visible. As damage progresses, it is clear that changes in the integrity of the specimen are monitored by the variations in the loading ramp of the impact load curve. The differences in these higher order modes of vibration indicate changes in the response of the composite as damage continues, as has been determined in structural testing by others [14]. Future efforts, combining impact fatigue testing and microwave NDI, will investigate the changes in the higher order modes of the impact pulse in an attempt to match impact damage signatures to damage intensity and location information from microwave maps.

CONCLUSIONS

Investigations of the initiation and propagation of damage in reinforced composite materials have been performed using the combination of impact fatigue testing and microwave imaging. The results are extremely promising as the microwave maps closely match the growing damage noted visually by an increased opacity of the glass fiber reinforced epoxy test specimens. Prior to the initiation of visible damage the scanning microwave technique was able to detect small regions, at the point of impact and at the warp/weave crossovers, which indicated changing properties and were clearly related to the morphology of the composite specimen. In addition, frequency information contained in variations in the load ramp of the impact pulse data also change with the degree of incremental damage.

While this technique has yet to be calibrated to generate quantitative information on the details of the degree of damage, the form and the depth, it is already apparent that the scanning microwave technique is capable of detecting extremely low levels of damage and has great potential for investigations of damage initiation and growth. By combining this technique with impact fatigue testing, damage growth can be monitored and compared to changes in the frequency response of the composite specimen. The relation of these effects may indicate a way to determine damage signatures for very low levels of damage, approaching the damage initiation region. Continued research is planned to attempt to gain further insight into the mechanisms of multiple impact, low energy damage in composite materials.

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